

Selective extraction of Cr^{3+} by aniline immobilized silica gel

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Abstract : Aniline immobilized silica gel has been prepared using silane coupling agent for the extraction of chromium from environmental samples with a view to reuse the metal. The Cr^{3+} binding capacity was found to be 8.7 mg g^{-1} even at trace level of chromium in aqueous solution and the value was 17.13 mg g^{-1} at relatively higher metal ion concentration. The presence of chloride ion improved the metal ion binding capacity as well as selectivity. The developed material and the selective extraction method were tested by applying it in real samples and the results were compared with the reported values. A special drive has been made to reuse the extracted chromium. The chemistry involved in selective extraction has been elucidated.

Keywords : Solid phase extraction, immobilization, recycling of chromium.

Introduction

Preparation of new adsorbent and its use in the selective extraction method is an important research area¹. A large number of researchers are engaged in the selective extraction of chromium²⁻⁷. But very few of them were interested in the reuse of the extracted metal⁸⁻¹⁰. Recycling of the waste metal ion makes the nature green.

Silica gel is a widely used support materials for its pendant Si-OH groups, allowing variety of ligands to be immobilized on the surface through coupling agents¹¹. Aniline immobilized silica gel is expected to be good binder for Cr^{3+} due to availability of electron rich nitrogen donor centre. Pavan *et al.*^{12,13} synthesized thermally stable aniline/silica composite through sol-gel technique for the adsorption of CoCl_2 , ZnCl_2 and CdCl_2 . Jacques and his co-workers⁴ grafted aniline moiety onto silica gel for the removal of Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} from aqueous solution. Kumar *et al.*⁵ synthesized amine-based polymer, aniline formaldehyde condensate (AFC) was coated on silica gel and used as an adsorbent for removal of Cr^{III} in aqueous medium. A new unbreakable solid phase micro-extraction (SPME) fiber coating based on poly(aniline)-silica nanocomposite was electrodeposited on a stainless steel wire⁷. However, the low Cr^{3+} uptake capacity, poor selectivity, slow adsorption rate and silence about the

reuse of the metal make the reported materials unsuitable for practical applications. In fact the reported materials are far from large enough to be utilized for the treatment of tannery effluent, which is the main source of chromium pollution.

Cr^{6+} is a well known carcinogen and Cr^{3+} is relatively inert. However, aerial oxidation, particularly in presence of soil, Cr^{3+} is converted to Cr^{6+} almost quantitatively¹⁴. Cr^{3+} is an essential to mammals that helps the body to control blood-sugar levels in trace concentrations, but toxic to fish when present in water above 5.0 mg L^{-1} ¹⁴. For compliance with this limit, it is essential for industries to treat their effluents to reduce the chromium to acceptable levels. The removal and reuse of the chromium content of this effluent is necessary for environmental protection and economic reasons.

In the present study, we have immobilized silica gel with aniline through functionalization the former by (3-chloropropyl)trimethoxysilane (3-CPTS) to achieve selective solid phase adsorbent for simultaneous removal and recovery of Cr^{3+} from aqueous solution. A special drive has been made to reuse the metal ion. The synthesized novel material and the developed extraction methodology have been tested in real environmental sample like tannery effluent.

synthesized novel material was studied by batch method. In a batch method, 0.2 g adsorbent (FSG@ANI) was taken in a conical flask along with 20 mL Cr³⁺ solution. The mixture was stirred at the rate of 90–100 rpm. The pH of the system was adjusted using acetic acid and sodium acetate buffer. The initial concentration of Cr³⁺ was kept to 5–1000 mg L⁻¹. After suitable time interval, the adsorbent was filtered and the residual solution was analyzed for Cr³⁺ ions spectroscopically⁴. The amount of Cr³⁺ extracted was calculated using the relationship :

$$q_t = (W_i - W_f)/M \quad (1)$$

Here q_t is the amount of Cr³⁺ adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg g⁻¹) (uptake capacity). W_i and W_f are the initial and residual amount (mg) of Cr^{III} respectively. M is the mass (g) of the adsorbent (FSG@ANI) added. The analysis was repeated at least thrice to determine the uncertainties values.

The removal and recovery of Cr³⁺ from tannery effluent was made by column method. In a column method, the chromatographic column (column = 0.8 × 8 cm) was filled up with the developed material (FSG@ANI). Then the tannery effluent was poured in the column (pH was adjusted to 3.1). Then system was kept for certain time to reach to equilibrium at room temperature. The extracted Cr³⁺ was eluted with several eluents at the flow rate 1 mL min⁻¹.

Isotherm and kinetic study :

Isotherm studies were conducted by batch method at different temperatures 8, 30 and 55 °C. The initial concentrations of Cr³⁺ taken for this study were 5, 20, 40, 60, 75 and 90 mg L⁻¹, and the solution was adjusted to pH 3.1. After equilibrium adsorption, the samples were separated and analyzed for Cr³⁺ content.

Kinetic study was performed by batch method at different temperatures 8, 30 and 55 °C. The initial concentration of Cr³⁺ and pH of the solution were 40 mg L⁻¹ and 3.1 respectively. One mL sample solution was withdrawn each time from the reaction mixture by a syringe at a gap of fixed interval and Cr³⁺ was analyzed.

Selectivity test :

To measure the selectivity, Cr³⁺ ion sorption was measured in the presence of 200 fold molar excess of

Cr⁶⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ ions at a constant pH (3.1), temperature (30 °C), sorbent dose (10 g L⁻¹) and time (1 h). The selected competitive ions (Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺) are commonly found in tannery effluent. The selectivity (S)¹⁶ defined as : $S = X/Y$; where, $X = \text{Cr}^{3+}$ sorption in presence of competitive ion and $Y = \text{Cr}^{3+}$ sorption in absence of competitive ion.

Results and discussion

Evidence for aniline immobilization and chromium binding :

FTIR : The functionalization of SG (FSG) was confirmed by FTIR analysis as shown in Fig. 1b. The characteristic new peak at around 2958 cm⁻¹ due to C-H stretching of CH₂ group, which was absent in the spectrum of pure SG (Fig. 1a). Hence, SG was successfully modified by the silane coupling agent (3-CPTS). Immobilization of aniline on functionalized silica gel was confirmed by the FTIR spectrum of FSG@ANI (Fig. 1c). The spectrum showed the characteristic peaks at 3429, 1502, 1230 and 800 cm⁻¹, which were absent in the spectra of both SG and FSG. The peaks at 3429, 1502, 1230 and 800 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to N-H stretching, benzene ring vibration, C-N stretching and N-H bending respectively¹⁷. The characteristic new peaks thus provided to strong evidence of aniline immobilization on FSG. The uptake of Cr³⁺ by FSG@ANI was confirmed by the appearance of two new peaks at 465 and 580 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺ (Fig. 1d). The new peaks were due to Cr-Cl bond formation and Cr-N linkage respectively¹⁸.

TGA : The TGA traces of SG, FSG, FSG@ANI and FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺ are presented in Fig. 2. SG exhibited two stage weight losses while its derivatives showed thrice. The initial weight loss of all the materials (from 40 °C to 100 °C) was mainly due to the loss of water¹⁶. The initial weight loss of SG (11.048%) was greater than it's all the derivatives (1.8794%, 1.509% and 2.062% weight reduction for FSG, FSG@ANI and FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺ respectively). The less weight loss in the later case suggested the conversion of Si-OH group of SG into Si-O-Si linkage in the derivatives (Scheme 1). In fact, the formation of Si-O-Si linkage explains the better thermal stability of the derivatives over SG. It was evident that the

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of (a) SG, (b) FSG, (c) FSG@ANI and (d) FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺.

Fig. 2. TGA curves of SG, FSG, FSG@ANI and FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺.

product FSG@ANI showed better thermal stability than FSG (the former undergoes less weight loss than later). FSG contains covalent chlorine, which is probably responsible for its relatively higher weight loss. Thus the result supports the reaction (Scheme 2), which deals with the conversion of C-Cl into C-N bond. The less thermal stability of the chromium loaded sample (FSG@ANI@Cr³⁺) may be due to catalytic activity of chromium (oxide) formed.

Effect of initial Cr³⁺ concentration :

The effect of initial Cr³⁺ concentration on its uptake by the synthesized novel material was investigated within the range 5–1000 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 3). The metal ion uptake increased steeply with the increase of metal ion concentration and became optimum at 1000 mg L⁻¹. The optimum uptake capacity was found to be 17.13 mg g⁻¹, which is superior to the value observed by Jacques *et al.*⁴ and commercially available ion exchange resin¹⁶ at simi-

Fig. 5. Adsorption isotherm at different temperature : [Adsorbent = 10 g L⁻¹, pH = 3.1, Time = 1 h] (RSD : 3.5 ± 0.3%, Confidence level : 97%).

Table 1. Values of Langmuir and Freundlich constants for the adsorption of Cr³⁺

T (K)	Langmuir constants				Freundlich constants		
	R _L	Q _m	b	R ²	n	K _F	R ²
281	5.88 × 10 ⁻¹	4.37	0.14	0.9758	4.98	1.72	0.9685
303	5.40 × 10 ⁻¹	4.70	1.7	0.9881	4.94	1.89	0.9649
328	5.0 × 10 ⁻¹	5.17	0.20	0.9883	5.12	2.21	0.9839

enthalpy (ΔH°), and entropy (ΔS°) change of adsorption were evaluated from the Van't Hoff equation³. The values of ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated from the slope and intercept of the Van't Hoff plot ($\ln K_c$ vs $1/T$). The calculated values are given in Table 2. The Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) values were found to be negative, which indicated the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process. In addition, more negative value of ΔG° with the increase of temperature justified the results of higher extent of adsorption at higher temperature. The positive value of ΔH° (0.61 kJ mol⁻¹) suggested an endothermic nature of Cr³⁺ adsorption. The positive values of ΔS°

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of Cr³⁺ on the FSG@ANI

T (K)	ln K _c	ΔG ^o (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH ^o (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS ^o (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
281	1.78	-6.60		
303	1.85	-7.17	0.61	25.69
328	2.06	-7.81		

(25.69 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) showed the increased randomness at the solid-solution interface during the adsorption process.

Effect of contact time : kinetic measurement :

Fig. 6 shows the amount of Cr³⁺ uptake (q_t , mg g⁻¹) at different contact time. Almost 95% uptake took place within 35 min and the time required to reach the equilibrium was 40 min. The rapid uptake was probably due to the availability of electron rich nitrogen donor centre of FSG@ANI. Similar type of observation was made at the temperatures 8, 30 and 55 °C. The time-dependent experimental data (Fig. 6) were used to fit various kinetic models¹⁴ through linear regression plots. The linear re-

Fig. 6. Variation of Cr³⁺ uptake capacity with time and temperature : [Adsorbent = 10 g L⁻¹, C₀ = 40 mg L⁻¹, pH = 3.1] (RSD : 2.5 ± 0.2%, Confidence level : 97%).

gression values ($R^2 > 0.95$) indicated that the Cr³⁺ adsorption fitted 2nd order, power function and simple Elovich equation satisfactorily. Fitting of 2nd order equation justified the observed metal ion binding mechanism (eq. (2)). The contact time required for maximum Cr³⁺ adsorption was found to be nearly 1 h. This equilibrium time is much less than many synthetic adsorbents and commercially available cation exchangers (Table 3).

Selectivity :

The selectivity test was performed with the competitive cations like Cr⁶⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ commonly found in tannery effluent. The selectivity value was found to be 1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 0.75, 0.8 and 0.7 for Cr⁶⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Al³⁺ respectively.

Table 3. Comparison of uptake capacities of Cr^{3+} with various adsorbents

Adsorbents	Uptake capacity (mg g^{-1})	pH	Optimum adsorption time (h)	C_0 (mg L^{-1}) (Initial concentration of Cr^{3+})	Reference
Chinese reed (<i>Miscanthus Sinensis</i>)	1.32	4	1	40	2
Sporopollenin based resins	4.4-5.2	5.0	24	52	3
Aniline grafted silica gel	16.02	4.5	2	1000	4
Aniline formaldehyde condensate (AFC)	3.25	5	2	45	5
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp. Biomass	2.24	4	48	≥ 50	6
Coir pith	11.44	3.3	1.30	≥ 50	20
Bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinic acid	5.83	4.6	4	60	21
Active sludge of a biogas plant	7.8	2.5	3	≥ 40	22
Cross-linked chitosan	5.72	4.0	96	20	23
Aniline immobilized onto functionalized silica gel (Present material)	8.7	3.1	0.66	40	Present work
	17.13			1000	work

Since the selectivity value was greater than 0.5, it may be concluded that the material exhibits higher preference¹⁶ towards chromium metal. The synthesized material showed the selectivity order as : $\text{Cr}^{3+} > \text{Fe}^{3+} > \text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} \gg \text{Cr}^{6+}, \text{Na}^+$ and Mg^{2+} . The higher preference of Cr^{3+} may be explained on the basis of complex formation as described in eq. (2). Fe^{3+} , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} did not form similar type of complex due to low crystal field stabilization energy (CFSE) and devoid of *d*-orbitals respectively. Na^+ and Mg^{2+} ions are not a transition metal and Cr^{6+} exists as anion in aqueous medium. So, the ions that are commonly present in tannery effluent did not affect the uptake of Cr^{3+} .

Effect of chloride ion on Cr^{3+} binding :

The effect of Cr^{3+} uptake capacity in presence of chloride ions was shown in Fig. 7. The Cr^{3+} binding capacity of the synthesized material was increased almost two folds in presence of 0.004 M chloride ions. The observed uptake capacity was enhanced to 8.7 mg g^{-1} (at trace level chromium), which was higher than many synthetic adsorbents and commercially available cation exchangers (Table 3). The chloride ions probably help in binding the Cr^{3+} through occupying thrice co-ordination sites with the immobilized aniline (Scheme 3). The structure **A** suggested the binding of one Cr^{3+} atom per two nitrogen centre while the **B** indicated one Cr^{3+} atom per each nitrogen centre. Then structure **B** explained the two fold increase of Cr^{3+} up taking. It is note worthy men-

Fig. 7. Variation of uptake capacity (q_t) with chloride anions : (■) In the presence of chloride ions; (■) In the absence of chloride ions : [Adsorbent = 10 g L^{-1} , Anions conc. = 0.004 M , Temperature = $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Time = 1 h] (RSD : $3.5 \pm 0.2\%$, Confidence level : 98%).

tion here that the presence of chloride not only helped in increasing Cr^{3+} binding, but also influenced the selectivity of the material. Literature survey also revealed that there are thousands of Cr^{3+} complexes with amines and chlorides having the formula $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{L}$ (octahedral) (where $\text{L} = \text{amines}$)¹⁹.

Removal and recovery of Cr^{3+} from tannery effluent :

To evaluate the accuracy and applicability of the developed material and method, it was tested with simulated tannery effluent. The Cr^{3+} containing synthetic tan-

Scheme 3. Uptake capacity of Cr^{3+} in presence of chloride ions.

nery effluent was prepared as per literature² and its composition and results were presented in Table 4. It was found that the chromium contamination became below permissible limit¹⁴ after successful treatment of the effluent by column method. It was found that 0.1 M NaOH

Table 4. Treatment of synthetic tannery effluent

[Column : internal diameter 0.8 cm, bed height 8 cm, flow rate = 1 mL min⁻¹, pH = 3.1, Temp. = 30 °C]

Parameter	Value (mg L ⁻¹) (Before applying synthetic sample)	Value (mg L ⁻¹) ^a (After applying synthetic sample)
Cr^{3+}	40	1.49
Fe^{3+}	0.4	0.37
Al^{3+}	11.0	10.97
Na^+	2810	2800
Cl^-	3654	1195
SO_4^{2-}	1180	1174
TOC (as acetic acid)	170	170

^aAverage of five determinations.

(RSD : 1.5 ± 0.2%, Confidence level : 98%).

along with hydrogen peroxide is the most effective eluents among the used eluents (NaOH, NH_4OH , Na_2CO_3 and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$). The efficiency of the present method (17.13 mg g⁻¹) is superior to other adsorbents (Table 3) in the sense of low Cr^{3+} uptake capacity, poor selectivity, slow adsorption rate and silence about the reuse of the metal. Before the new exhaustion cycle, the prepared material is reactivated by passing water through the bed. The present material could be regenerated as for 30 cycles with the little loss of chromium binding capacity. It was observed that there was a loss of 10% efficiency after 30 cycles.

Reuse of the extracted chromium :

The traditional techniques used for metal recovery are based on chemical precipitation coupled to pre or post oxidation/reduction followed by filtration in order to concentrate the species of interest. These techniques are the production of solid residues (sludge's) containing toxic metals whose final disposal is in general land filling. We developed a method for removal and reuse of Cr^{3+} from tannery wastewater (Scheme 4). The extracted Cr^{3+} was eluted quantitatively by the NaOH and hydrogen peroxide mixture in the form of Cr^{6+} . Then it was reduced back to Cr^{3+} by calculated amount of sulfurous acid.

Scheme 4. An overview on the steps of reuse of Cr^{3+} .

Finally the resulted solution was recrystallized as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, which may be reused. The present method is simple in the sense that there is no necessity for regeneration of column like other methods such as IERECHROM process⁸, ion-exchange⁹ and electrochemical oxidation¹⁰.

Conclusions

A new solid phase adsorbent based on immobilizing aniline onto silica gel surface through functionalizing the

later by 3-CPTS has been synthesized through green approach. Novelty of the present scheme is that it did not require additives, organic solvent and costly gas. The developed green approach eliminated the step of activation by prolonged acid treatment.

Higher uptake capacity (17.13 and 8.7 mg g⁻¹ at higher and trace level of Cr³⁺ respectively), faster rate of metal ion extraction (40 min), improved selectivity and easy regeneration makes the material superior to many synthetic adsorbents and commercially available exchangers. The material may be used up to 30 cycles with the little loss of efficiency.

Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm fit well to explain the Cr³⁺ adsorption by FSG@ANI. The adsorption process follows the 2nd order kinetics, which justifies the metal ion binding mechanism successfully. The thermodynamic parameters suggest favorable and an endothermic nature of Cr³⁺ adsorption.

The developed material and the extraction method may be applied successfully for the removal, recovery and reuse of chromium from the tannery effluent. Selective extraction, quantitative elution and efficient re-crystallization of the chromium salt are the salient features of the present reuse scheme.

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